

NON FICTIONAL AND SCARED WAYS TO MANAGE LIFE SKILLS

(Laid down 1450 years ago by untutored Prophet)

Dr Ashfaq Ahmad Khan**Abstract**

Life skills are abilities for adaptive and positive behavior that enable humans to deal effectively with the demands and challenges of life. This concept is also termed as psychosocial competency. What the 21st century is expecting and inculcating from mankind. In this materialistic world, life skills are associated with promotional activities; it may be promotion of commodities, businesses and ideas. It's very objective is customary and professional in approach. An attempt has been made to compile some imperative, contemporary, empirical and fool proof life skills laid down by the Prophet Mohammad (SAW) some 1450 years ago. Be it Social, Cultural, Economical or Religious provided standards to mankind. Above all the Almighty gave them a certificate of success and made them a benchmark for the rest of mankind. From tribes they became Companions of the Prophet Mohammad (SAW) Therefore an effort has been made to compile those lost, unconventional, sacred and divine skills followed by earlier Muslims. May Allah make it a source of inspiration for all us. For example, the following are few teachings of Prophet Mohammad (SAW). Ayesha Radiyallahu 'anha narrated that Prophet Mohammad (SAW) ordered us to treat people according to their status. (Sahih Muslim). Jabir ibne-'Abdullah Radiyallahu 'anhu narrated that Prophet Mohammad (SAW) prayed May Allah confer mercy upon a man who is kindly, when selling, when buying and when demanding his balance. (Bukhari). Abu Hurairah Radhiyallahu 'anhu narrates that Prophet Mohammad (SAW) said: A Believer's soul is attached (preventing his entry to Paradise) to his debt till it is paid. (Tirmidhi)

Key words:

Life skills, Prophet Mohammad, Sahaba-(Companion), Hadith-(Saying of Prophet SAW), Quran, Islam, Sallalaha ahiwa sallam(SAW)-(Peace be upon him), Radiyallahu 'anhu (RA) May the Almighty be pleased with him.

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Introduction

“The term ‘Life Skills’ refers to the skills you need to make the most out of life.”

Life skills are abilities for adaptive and positive behavior that enable humans to deal effectively with the demands and challenges of life. This concept is also termed as psychosocial competency. The subject varies greatly depending on social norms and community expectations but skills that function for well-being and aid individuals to develop into active and productive members of their communities are considered as life skills.

The World Health Organization in 1999 identified the following core cross-cultural areas of life skills:

- Decision-making and problem-solving;
- Creative thinking and critical thinking;
- Communication and interpersonal skills;
- Self-awareness and empathy;

- Assertiveness and equanimity; and
- Resilience and coping with emotions and coping with stress.

The above few lines depicts what the 21st century is expecting and inculcating from mankind.

In this materialistic world, life skills are associated with promotional activities; it may be promotion of commodities, businesses and ideas. It's very objective is customary and professional in approach. Because of shortsightedness in the idea behind it, the real charm or the fascination is lost. Therefore rules, behavior, social services etc which a person follows, the moment its objective is achieved or purpose is solved will start acting in a selfish way. The life skills followed are circumstantial in nature and not everlasting due to its myopic objective. The projected behavior is superficial or cosmetic in nature. These life skills are influenced by a number of factors may be monetary, nature of Job, rules and regulation etc.

Objective

The objective is to compile and put forward some imperative, contemporary, empirical and foolproof life skills laid down by the Prophet Mohammad (SAW) some 1450 years ago. He preached these life skills among the most neglected, uncivilized, undeveloped, uncultured people during that period on the earth. And within a short period of 23 years he transformed them into one of the most exemplary people on the planet for all mankind from every perspective. Be it Social, Cultural, Economical or Religious provided standards to mankind. Above all the Almighty gave them a certificate of success and made them a benchmark for the rest of mankind. From tribes they became Companions of the Prophet Mohammad ﷺ (SAW).

These life skills are sacred, revealed, prophetic and divine in nature. The motivating factors to inculcate these factors are faith for reward, respect and peaceful life in both the world. These life skills are prescribed by God and his messenger. Practicing those carries tremendous reward here and hereafter.

It is obvious from above that the first Muslims had attained that position in life because of the purity and strength of their faith and the excellence of their character and conduct.

Therefore an effort has been made to compile those lost, unconventional, sacred and divine skills followed by earlier Muslims. May Allah make it a source of inspiration for all us.

Collection of 40 Hadith for different walks of life:

1. Ayesha Radiyallahu 'anha narrated that Prophet Mohammad ﷺ (SAW) ordered us to treat people according to their status. (Sahih Muslim)
2. Harithah ibn-Wahab Radiyallahu 'anhu narrates: I heard Prophet Mohammad ﷺ (SAW) saying: Should I not inform you of the people of Paradise? Anyone who is weak, not harsh in dealings and behavior, but moderate and soft; people (also) consider him unimportant, (but he is so close to Allah that) if he swears by Allah, He will fulfill his words. And the dwellers of Hell are miserly, insolent and arrogant. (Bukhari)
3. Abu Sa'id Radiyallahu'anhu narrated that Prophet Mohammad ﷺ (SAW) said: A truthful trustworthy merchant shall be with the Prophets, *Siddiqin* (the true followers) and martyrs. (Tirmidhi)
4. Allah says: And the true servants of Rahman (the most gracious Allah) are they who walk on the earth with humility. (Al-Furqan 25:63)
5. Allah says: And whenever they get angry, they readily forgive. (Al Quran-Surat us-Shura 42:37)

6. Abu Hurairah Radiyallahu 'anhu narrates. that Prophet Mohammad ﷺ (SAW) said: The most perfect amongst the believers in faith is one who has the best manners; and the best of you are those who are best to their wives. (MusnadAhmad)
7. Abu Darda'Radiyallahu 'anhu narrated that Prophet Mohammad ﷺ (SAW) said: There will be nothing heavier on the Scale than good conduct. (Abu Dawud)
8. 'Abdullah ibne-Mas'ud Radiyallahu 'anhu narrates that Prophet Mohammad ﷺ (SAW) said: Shall I not inform you about the person who is forbidden from the Fire and for whom the Fire is forbidden? Anyone who's close to people, soft and lenient. (Tirmidhi)
{Note: The hadith implies that such a person freely mixes with people is soft spoken and because of his qualities, people also meet him with love and without reservations..(Muarif-ul-Hadith)}
9. Anas Radiyallahu 'anhu narrates that none was dearer to the Sahabah than Prophet Mohammad ﷺ (SAW) yet when they saw him, they did not stand up, knowing his dislike for this. (Tirmidhi)
10. Abu Hurairah Radiyallahu 'anhu narrated that Prophet Mohammad ﷺ (SAW) said: Musa ibne-Imran 'Alaihis Salam said:O my Rabb! Who is the most respectable slave to you? Allah the Almighty and Majestic replied: He who forgives, despite having the power to avenge. (Baihaqi)
11. Abu Qatadah Radiyallahu 'anhu narrates: I heard (SAW) ﷺ saying: If anyone likes that Allah should save him from the anxieties of the Day of Resurrection, he should grant respite (in paying back a loan) to one who is in constraints, or forgo the debt. (Muslim)
12. Jabir ibne-'Abdullah Radiyallahu 'anhu narrated that Prophet Mohammad ﷺ (SAW) prayed May Allah confer mercy upon a man who is kindly, when selling, when buying and when demanding his balance. (Bukhari)
13. Allah says: O you who believe! Stand out firmly for justice and bear true witnesses according to the will of Allah, even though it be against yourselves, or your parents, or your kin. Whether the person concerned is rich (I should benefit him), or poor (out of sympathy I should favor him), Allah is a better protector of both than you. So do not be led by your personal desires in fulfilling justice. If you distort your witness or refuse to give it, verily Allah is well acquainted with all that you do. (An Nisa 135- Quran)
14. 'Abdullah Radiyallahu'anhu narrated that Prophet Mohammad ﷺ (SAW) said: The one who offers Salam (greetings) first is free from arrogance...(Baihaqi)
15. Abdullah ibne-'Amr ibnil Shoab Radiyallahu'anhu narrates that Prophet Mohammad ﷺ (SAW) said: One must not sit between two persons without their permission.(Abu Dawud)
16. Ka'b ibne-Malik Radiyallahu 'anhu narrated that Prophet Mohammad ﷺ (SAW) said: He who visits a sick person enters into the Mercy of Allah; if he sits by his side, he is immersed in the Mercy.(Musnad Ahmad) 'Amr ibne-Hazm Radiyallahu 'anhu narrates: Even after leaving the sick ,the visit or continues to be in the Mercy of Allah until he returns to the place from where he had come. (Tabarani, Majma-'uz-Zawaid)
17. Anas Radiyallahu'anhu narrated that Prophet Mohammad ﷺ (SAW) said:None of you is a true believer, until he likes for his brother what he likes for himself. (Bukhari)
18. Hudhaifah Radiyallahu 'anhu narrates that Prophet Mohammad ﷺ (SAW) said: Do not imitate others and start saying if others treat us well, we will treat them well, and if they do wrong to us, we will do wrong to them; but accustom yourself to do good if people do good, and not to do wrong if they do wrong. (Tirmidhi)

19. Anas Radiyallahu'anhu narrates that Prophet Mohammad ﷺ (SAW) said: Help your Muslim brother whether he is an oppressor oppressed .A man asked:O Rasulullah! I Will Help him when he is oppressed,but how can I Help Him When He is an oppressor? He Replied:You stop or prevent him from oppression for indeed that is your help to him.(Bukhari)
20. Jubair ibne-Murtm Radiyallahu'anhu narrated that Prophet Mohammad (SAW) ﷺ said:He is not from us who calls towards 'Asabiyyah, He is not from us who flights out of 'Asabiyyah and he who dies upholding 'Asabiyyah, (AbuDawud)
- Note: 'Asabiyyah. Means fanatical association on the basis of language, tribe,race or nation.*
21. Abu Hurairah Radhiyallahu 'anhu narrates that Prophet Mohammad ﷺ (SAW) said: A Believer's soul is attached (preventing his entry to Paradise) to his debt till it is paid. (Tirmidhi)
22. Abu Hurairah Radiyallahu 'anhu narrated that Prophet Mohammad(SAW) said: He who does not thank people, does not thank Allah. (Tirmidhi)
23. A'ishah Radiyallahu'anha narrated that Prophet Mohammad(SAW) said: Who so ever assumed the responsibility of (managing) the affair of his daughters and treated them well,then these daughters will become shield for him from the Fire. (Bukhari)
24. Ayyub Rahimahullah on the authority of his father,who from his grandfather, narrated that Prophet Mohammad (SAW) said:No father gives his son any gift better than good education. (Tirmidhi)
25. Abu Hurairah Radiyallahu 'anhu narrated that Prophet Mohammad (SAW) said: Give presents (Gifts/ Hadayah) to one another, for a present removes hatred from the breast and a woman should not despise a gift from her neighbour, even if it is a portion of a goat's hoof. (Tirmidhi)
26. Abu Hurairah Radiyallahu 'anhu narrated that Prophet Mohammad (SAW) said: He Will not enter Paradise whose neighbour feels unsafe from his injurious conduct. (Muslim)
27. Abdullah ibn- 'Umar Radi Allahu 'anhuma narrated that Prophet Mohammad ﷺ (SAW) said: Pay the laborer his wages before his sweat dries. (Ibne-Majah)
28. Allah Subhanahu wa Ta'ala says: Indeed, Allah enjoins justice, Ihsan(doing good) and generosity towards kinsfolk; and forbids immorality, all evil deeds and oppression. He strongly exhorts you so that you might bear (all this)in mind. (An Nahl : 90)
- Note: In one sense this is the most comprehensive verse of the Quran. Three things have been advised: 1. Justice 2. Ihsan, 3.Generosity to relatives.And Three Things have been forbidden; 1.Immorality 2.All evil deeds 3.Oppression.Ihsan means that a man becomes a model of excellence desiring good for others. It is a station above justice when a man gives more than the rights due to others. He acquires the qualities of generosity, forgiveness and sympathy*
29. Anas ibne-Malik Radiyallahu 'anhu narrated that Prophet Mohammad ﷺ (SAW)said: He who likes his livelihood to be increased, and his life prolonged, should kindly fulfill the rights of his relatives. (Bukhari)
30. Allah subhanahu wa Ta'ala said: Woe to every slanderer and fault-finder. (Ibne Hibban)
31. Abu Hurairah Radiyallahu 'anhu narrated that Prophet Mohammad(SAW) ﷺ said:Whosoever hoards grain to raise its price for Muslims is a sinner.(Musnad Ahmad, Majma-'uz-Zawaid)

32. Abdullah ibne-'Umar Radiyallahu 'anhuma narrates that Prophet Mohammad ﷺ (SAW) said: He who raises weapons at us, is not from us. (Muslim)
33. Yazid Radiyallahu 'anhu narrated that Prophet Mohammad ﷺ (SAW) said: Undoubtedly none of you should take the belongings of his brother, neither in amusement nor seriously. (Abu Dawud)
34. Abdullah ibne-Mas'ud Radiyallahu 'anhu narrated that Prophet Mohammad ﷺ (SAW) said: It is not befitting for a believer to curse others. (Tirmidhi)
35. Abu Darda' Radiyallahu 'anhu narrated that Prophet Mohammad ﷺ (SAW) said: He who mentions a fault in a person, which is not present in him so as to defame him, Allah will detain him in Hell-fire till he proves what he said. (Tabarani, Majma Uz-Zawaid)
36. Abu Hurairah Radhiyallahu 'anhu narrates that Prophet Mohammad ﷺ (SAW) said: There are three signs of a hypocrite: When he speaks, he lies; when he promises, he breaks it; when he is entrusted, he violated the trust. (Muslim)
37. Imran ibne-Husain Radiyallahu 'anhuma narrated that Prophet Mohammad ﷺ (SAW) said: Whoever plunders is not from us. (Tirmidhi)
38. Humaid ibne-Abdur Rahman narrates from his mother Radiyallahu 'anha that Prophet Mohammad ﷺ (SAW) said: He who has spoken untruthfully to strike a reconciliation between two people has not lied. (Abu Dawud)
39. Abu Hurairah Radiyallahu 'anhu narrates that Prophet Mohammad ﷺ (SAW) said: He is not from us who instigates a woman against her husband, or a slave against his master. (Abu Dawood)
40. Urs ibne-'Umairah Al Kindi Radiyallahu 'anhu narrated that Prophet Mohammad ﷺ (SAW) said: When a sin is committed on the earth; he who sees it and disapproves it, will be like the one who wasn't present. And the one who wasn't present when the sin was committed but approves of it, will like the one who was present there. (Abu Dawud)

Conclusion

May The Almighty shower his bounties on the companions who recorded, memorized and saved every aspect of beloved Prophet Mohammad ﷺ (SAW) for the guidance of mankind in both the world. These are few selected teachings of the Prophet. While going through this we can understand their relevance in today's world for peaceful life be it personal, social, economical, spiritual or formal engagement. An effort was made to compile those lost, unconventional, sacred and divine skills followed by earlier followers of Islam. May the almighty Allah (God) make it a source of inspiration for all us.

References

Books of Hadiths: Bukhari Abu Dawud, Muslim etc

Muntakhab Ahadith

<https://www.life-skillsyouneed.com/general/life-skills.html>